

Lepidoptera fauna of Kunashir Island (Russia): Update 2025

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Abstract

In the present study, the twenty-eight Lepidoptera species are recorded from Kunashir Island for the first time (one of them, *Chibidokuga hypenodes* Inoue, 1979, is also new record to the fauna of Russia). Additionally, the occurrences of *Eurydoxa advena* Filipjev, 1930, *Stigmatophora leacrita* (Swinhoe, 1894) and *Zanclognatha obliqua* Staudinger, 1892 on the Kuril Islands are confirmed.

Keywords

Biodiversity, island biogeography, Kuril Islands, Russian Far East, first record, *Chibidokuga hypenodes*

Introduction

Despite the Lepidoptera fauna of Kunashir Island being actively studied, it remains poorly understood. This may be a consequence of the fact that localities remote from the sea (> 500 m from the shoreline) are insufficiently examined by entomologists, as supported by our recent records (Koshkin et al. 2023; Spitsyna and Spitsyn 2023a, b; Spitsyna et al. 2024). In the meantime, localities near the sea coast (ca. 80–250 m from the shoreline), in contrast, are the most well-studied (e.g. Rybalkin and Yakovlev 2017; Rybalkin et al. 2018, 2019, 2022; Dubatolov 2019a; Rybalkin 2020a, b; Dubatolov et al. 2023; Dubatolov and Zinchenko 2024).

This study aims to report on the twenty-eight new records of Lepidoptera species from Kunashir Island (one of them, *Chibidokuga hypenodes* Inoue, 1979, is also new record to the fauna of Russia) and to confirm the occurrences of *Eurydoxa advena* Filipjev, 1930, *Stigmatophora leacrita* (Swinhoe, 1894) and *Zanclognatha obliqua* Staudinger, 1892 on the Kuril Islands. All species listed below are known from Hokkaido, except for *Parocneria furva* (Leech, [1889]) and *Daddala lucilla* (Butler, 1881). Therefore, these findings on Kunashir Island seem quite expectable.

Materials and methods

This study is based on materials from the collection of the Russian Museum of Biodiversity Hotspots (RMBH), N. Laverov Federal Center for Integrated Arctic Research of the Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences (Arkhangelsk, Russia) and the private collection of Evgeny S. Koshkin (Khabarovsk, Russia). The genitalia were dissected, mounted on temporary glass slides with 70% ethanol, and photographed using a Leica M165C stereomicroscope with a FLEXACAM C1 digital camera and a Zeiss Stemi 2000-C stereomicroscope with a Zeiss AxioCam ERC5s microscope camera, then preserved in glycerin in micro-tubes pinned to the specimens. Images of the specimens were taken using a Canon EOS 7D camera with a Canon EF 100mm f/2.8L Macro IS USM lens and a Sony SLT-A65 digital camera with a Sony 2.8/50 Macro lens.

Results

Family Lycaenidae Leach, 1815

Chrysozephyrus brilliantinus (Staudinger, 1887)

Figs 1A, 6A

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: Ozerny cordon, small broad-leaved forest with Kuril bamboo (*Sasa kurilensis*), 43°52'26"N, 145°28'56"E, 05–07.08.2022, A. Kostyunin & V. Bezborodov leg., 1♂.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands.

***Chrysozephyrus smaragdinus* (Bremer, 1861)**

Fig. 1B

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: Tretyakovo village, coniferous and broad-leaved forest, 43°58'52"N, 145°39'12"E, 18.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 1♀.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands.

Family Tortricidae Latreille, 1803

***Eurydoxa advena* Filipjev, 1930**

Fig. 1C

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: Andreevsky cordon, edge of broad-leaved forest and seaside meadows, 43°53'16"N, 145°37'28"E, 27–28.07.2022, A. Kostyunin leg., 1♀; Tretyakovo village, cottages on the edge of coniferous and broad-leaved forest and seaside meadows, 43°59'13"N, 145°39'12"E, 26–27.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 1♀; Tretyakovo village, coniferous and broad-leaved forest, 43°58'52"N, 145°39'12"E, 01.08.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 1♀.

Remark. The species has already been recorded from the eastern coast of Kunashir Island and Shikotan Island (Krivolutskaya 1973; Sinev and Nedoshivina 2016). Our findings from the western coast of Kunashir Island expand the understanding of the species' range in the Southern Kuril Islands.

Family Sphingidae Latreille, 1802

***Dolbina exacta* Staudinger, 1892**

Figs 1D, 6B

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: Tretyakovo village, cottages on the edge of coniferous and broad-leaved forest and seaside meadows, 43°59'13"N, 145°39'12"E, 26–31.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 2♂; the same locality and collectors, 01–05.08.2025, 1♂.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands. Previously, the species was recorded based on two misidentified male specimens of *Dolbina tancrei* Staudinger, 1887 (Rybalkin and Yakovlev 2017; Rybalkin et al. 2022).

***Phyllosphingia dissimilis* (Bremer, 1861)**

Fig. 1E

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: territory surrounding the airport, coniferous-birch forest with Kuril bamboo (*Sasa kurilensis*), 43°58'22"N, 145°41'03"E, 07–08.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 1♂.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands.

Family Erebidae Leach, 1815

Subfamily Arctiinae Leach, 1815

***Stigmatophora leacrita* (Swinhoe, 1894)**

Fig. 2A

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: Tretyakovo village, cottages on the edge of coniferous and broad-leaved forest and seaside meadows, 43°59'13"N, 145°39'12"E, 19–20.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 2♀; the same locality and collectors, 20–21.07.2025, 2♂.

Remark. The occurrence of *Stigmatophora leacrita* on the Kuril Islands hitherto remained unclear (Dubatolov 2019b) but it is confirmed here by our records.

***Stigmatophora rhodophila* (Walker, 1864)**

Fig. 2B

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: territory surrounding the airport, coniferous-birch forest with Kuril bamboo (*Sasa kurilensis*), 43°58'22"N, 145°41'03"E, 17–18.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 1♀.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands.

***Macrobrotis staudingeri* (Alphéraky, 1897)**

Fig. 2C

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: territory surrounding the airport, coniferous-birch forest with Kuril bamboo (*Sasa kurilensis*), 43°58'22"N, 145°41'03"E, 01–02.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & A. Kostyunin leg., 1♂; Tretyakovo village, cottages on the edge of coniferous and broad-leaved forest and seaside meadows, 43°59'13"N, 145°39'12"E, 15–16.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 1♂.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands.

Figure 1. Species of the families Lycaenidae, Tortricidae, Sphingidae from Kunashir Island: **A** – *Chrysozephyrus brilliantinus*; **B** – *Chrysozephyrus smaragdinus*; **C** – *Eurydoxa advena*; **D** – *Dolbina exacta*; **E** – *Phyllosphingia dissimilis*. Scale bar = 10 mm.

***Nudina artaxidia* (Butler, 1881)**

Fig. 2D

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: Tretyakovo village, cottages on the edge of coniferous and broad-leaved forest and seaside meadows, 43°59'13"N, 145°39'12"E, 20–21.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 1♂, 1♀; the same locality and collectors, 22–23.07.2025, 1♂; the same locality and collectors, 23–24.07.2025, 1♂.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands.

Subfamily Lymantriinae Hampson, 1893

Telochurus recens (Hübner, 1819)

Fig. 2E

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: Tretyakovo village, cottages on the edge of coniferous and broad-leaved forest and seaside meadows, 43°59'13"N, 145°39'12"E, 04–05.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 1♂.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands.

Parocneria furva (Leech, [1889])

Fig. 2F

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: Tretyakovo village, cottages on the edge of coniferous and broad-leaved forest and seaside meadows, 43°59'13"N, 145°39'12"E, 16–17.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 3♂; the same locality and collectors, 18–19.07.2025, 1♂; the same locality and collectors, 22–23.07.2025, 1♂; the same locality and collectors, 23–24.07.2025, 1♂.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands. *Parocneria furva* is widespread in Japan but is unknown from Hokkaido (Kishida 2011a). Previously, there were only two records of this rare species from Russia, namely in the Yankovsky Peninsula in 1897 and in the Ussurisky Nature Reserve more than 50 years ago (Tschistjakov 1981, 2001). Larvae of *P. furva* feed on *Juniperus* spp. and *Chamaecyparis* spp. (Tschistjakov 2001).

Subfamily Erebinae Leach, 1815

Catocala bella Butler, 1877

Fig. 3A

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: Tretyakovo village, cottages on the edge of coniferous and broad-leaved forest and seaside meadows, 43°59'13"N, 145°39'12"E, 26–27.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 3♂; the same locality and collectors, 27–28.07.2025, 1♂.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands.

Catocala ella Butler, 1877

Fig. 3B

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: Tretyakovo village, cottages on the edge of coniferous and broad-leaved forest and seaside meadows, 43°59'13"N, 145°39'12"E, 26–27.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 1♂; the same locality and collectors, 27–28.07.2025, 1♂; the same locality and collectors, 28–29.07.2025, 3♂;

the same locality and collectors, 02–03.08.2025, 2♂; the same locality and collectors, 03–04.08.2025, 1♂, 2♀; the same locality and collectors, 04–05.08.2025, 2♂.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands.

Catocala nagioides Wileman, 1924

Fig. 3C

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: Tretyakovo village, cottages on the edge of coniferous and broad-leaved forest and seaside meadows, 43°59'13"N, 145°39'12"E, 26–31.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 3♂; the same locality and collectors, 01–05.08.2025, 9♂, 2♀.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands.

Daddala lucilla (Butler, 1881)

Fig. 3D

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: Tretyakovo village, seaside meadows near forest with low-growing oak trees, 43°59'30"N 145°38'56"E, 18–19.09.2023, G. Grigoriev leg., 1♀.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands. It should be noted that *Daddala lucilla* is unknown from Hokkaido (Kononenko 2010).

Melapia electaria (Bremer, 1864)

Fig. 4A

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: territory surrounding the airport, coniferous-birch forest with Kuril bamboo (*Sasa kurilensis*), 43°58'22"N, 145°41'03"E, 18–19.06.2025, V. Spitsyn & A. Kostyunin, 1♂; Tretyakovo village, cottages on the edge of coniferous and broad-leaved forest and seaside meadows, 43°59'13"N, 145°39'12"E, 25–26.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 1♂; the same locality and collectors, 27–28.07.2025, 1♂, 1♀.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands.

Blasticorhinus unduligera (Butler, 1878)

Figs 4B, 6C

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: Tretyakovo village, cottages on the edge of coniferous and broad-leaved forest and seaside meadows, 43°59'13"N, 145°39'12"E, 21–25.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 1♂; the same locality and collectors, 26–31.07.2025, 1♂.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands. *Blasticorhinus unduligera* is very externally similar to *B. ussuriensis* (Bremer, 1861) and can reliably be identified only by the male genitalia structure (Fig. 6C). *B. unduligera* was described from

Japan (Yokohama), but was subsequently considered as a junior synonym of *B. ussuriensis* for a long time. Due to this reason, *B. ussuriensis* was mentioned as occurring taxon in Japan in the large number of works (e.g. Inoue et al. 1982; Kishida et al. 2011; etc.) After examination of the type specimens of both taxa, it turned out that they are not conspecific and clearly differ from each other in the male genitalia (Kononenko, Han 2007; Kononenko 2010). *B. unduligera* and *B. ussuriensis* sympatrically occur in the mainland southern Russian Far East, Korea, and China, whereas in Japan only *B. unduligera* is known (Kononenko 2010; Watabiki et al. 2021). It is very likely that *B. ussuriensis* is also not distributed on the Kuril Islands.

Figure 2. Species of the family Erebidae from Kunashir Island: **A** – *Stigmatophora leacrita*; **B** – *Stigmatophora rhodophila*; **C** – *Macrobrochis staudingeri*; **D** – *Nudina artaxidia*; **E** – *Telochurus recens*; **F** – *Parocneria furva*. Scale bar = 10 mm.

Figure 3. Species of the family Erebidae from Kunashir Island: **A** – *Catocala bella*; **B** – *Catocala ella*; **C** – *Catocala nagioides*; **D** – *Daddala lucilla*. Scale bar = 10 mm.

Subfamily Hypocalinae Guenée, 1852

Hypocala subsatura Guenée, 1852

Fig. 4C

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: Otrada village, mixed forest, 44°05'04"N, 145°52'35"E, 29–30.06.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 1♂.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands. This specimen appears to be a migrant from the southern parts of its range.

Subfamily Herminiinae Leach, [1815]

Bertula bistrigata (Staudinger, 1888)

Fig. 4G

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: Tretyakovo village, cottages on the edge of coniferous and broad-leaved forest and seaside meadows, 43°59'13"N, 145°39'12"E, 11–15.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 1♂.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands.

Zanclognatha obliqua Staudinger, 1892

Fig. 4E

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: territory surrounding the airport, coniferous-birch forest with Kuril bamboo (*Sasa kurilensis*), 43°58'22"N, 145°41'03"E, 07–08.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna, 1♀.

Remark. Although the data on occurrence of *Zanclognatha obliqua* on Kunashir Island had been provided by Kononenko (2010), the other later works did not make reference to this data. The occurrence of *Z. obliqua* on the Kuril Islands is confirmed here by our record.

Subfamily Boletobiinae Guenée, [1858]

Diomea cremata (Butler, 1878)

Fig. 4F

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: Tretyakovo village, cottages on the edge of coniferous and broad-leaved forest and seaside meadows, 43°59'13"N, 145°39'12"E, 06–10.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 1♂.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands.

Chibidokuga hypenodes Inoue, 1979

Figs 4H–I, 6D

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: territory surrounding the airport, coniferous-birch forest with Kuril bamboo (*Sasa kurilensis*), 43°58'22"N, 145°41'03"E, 07–08.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna, 1♂; Tretyakovo village, cottages on the edge of coniferous and broad-leaved forest and seaside meadows, 43°59'13"N, 145°39'12"E, 16–20.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 1♂.

Remark. The first record of the species and genus from Russia. Previously, *Chibidokuga hypenodes* was known in Japan (including Hokkaido), China, and South Korea (Inoue 1979; Kononenko et al. 1998; Park et al. 2001; Kishida 2011b). The specimens from Kunashir Island have the male genitalia structure similar to those of specimens from Japan (Fig 6D).

Family Noctuidae Latreille, 1809

Subfamily Bryophilinae Guenée, 1852

Stenoloba jankowskii (Oberthür, 1884)

Fig. 4K

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: territory surrounding the airport, coniferous-birch forest with Kuril bamboo (*Sasa kurilensis*), 43°58'22"N,

145°41'03"E, 01–02.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & A. Kostyunin, 1♂; Tretyakovo village, cottages on the edge of coniferous and broad-leaved forest and seaside meadows, 43°59'13"N, 145°39'12"E, 16–20.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 2♂, 1♀; the same locality and collectors, 26–31.07.2025, 2♂, 1♀; the same locality and collectors, 01–05.08.2025, 1♂, 1♀.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands.

Subfamily Bagisarinae Crumb, 1956

Amyna punctum (Fabricius, 1794)

Figs 4D, 6E

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: territory surrounding the airport, coniferous-birch forest with Kuril bamboo (*Sasa kurilensis*), 43°58'22"N, 145°41'03"E, 20–21.06.2025, V. Spitsyn, E. Spitsyna & A. Kostyunin, 1♀.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands. The range of *Amyna punctum* covers Africa, Middle East, Australia, Oceania, Southeast Asia, China, Korea, and Japan. In Russia, the species is also known to occur in Primorsky Krai (Kononenko 2010).

Subfamily Condicinae Poole, 1995

Prometopus flavicollis (Leech, [1889])

Fig. 4J

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: territory surrounding the airport, coniferous-birch forest with Kuril bamboo (*Sasa kurilensis*), 43°58'22"N, 145°41'03"E, 01–02.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & A. Kostyunin, 1♀.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands.

Subfamily Noctuinae Latreille, 1809

Ipimorpha subtusa ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)

Fig. 4L

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: Tretyakovo village, cottages on the edge of coniferous and broad-leaved forest and seaside meadows, 43°59'13"N, 145°39'12"E, 26–31.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 1♀.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands.

***Cosmia pyralina* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)**

Fig. 5A

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: Tretyakovo village, cottages on the edge of coniferous and broad-leaved forest and seaside meadows, 43°59'13"N, 145°39'12"E, 11–15.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 1♂; the same locality and collectors, 16–20.07.2025, 1♂.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands.

***Cosmia cara* (Butler, 1881)**

Fig. 5B

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: Tretyakovo village, cottages on the edge of coniferous and broad-leaved forest and seaside meadows, 43°59'13"N, 145°39'12"E, 01–05.08.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 1♂.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands. In Russia, *Cosmia cara* is also known to occur in Primorsky Krai and the south of Khabarovsk Krai (Kononenko 2016).

***Chasminodes atrata* (Butler, 1884)**

Fig. 4M

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: Tretyakovo village, cottages on the edge of coniferous and broad-leaved forest and seaside meadows, 43°59'13"N, 145°39'12"E, 16–20.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 2♂; the same locality and collectors, 21–25.07.2025, 1♂.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands.

***Mormo muscivirens* Butler, 1878**

Fig. 5C

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: Tretyakovo village, cottages on the edge of coniferous and broad-leaved forest and seaside meadows, 43°59'13"N, 145°39'12"E, 21–25.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 1♀; the same locality and collectors, 26–31.07.2025, 1♂, 1♀.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands. In Russia, *Mormo muscivirens* is also known to occur in Primorsky Krai and the south of Khabarovsk Krai (Kononenko 2016).

***Orthogonia sera* Felder & Felder, 1862**

Fig. 5D

Material examined. RUSSIA, Kunashir Island: Tretyakovo village, cottages on the edge of coniferous and broad-leaved forest and seaside meadows, 43°59'13"N,

145°39'12"E, 21–25.07.2025, V. Spitsyn & E. Spitsyna leg., 1♀; the same locality and collectors, 26–31.07.2025, 1♂, 2♀.

Remark. The first record from the Kuril Islands and the second record from Russia. Previously, *Orthogonia sera* was recorded from the south of Primorsky Krai based on a single female specimen (Kononenko 2005, 2016).

Figure 4. Species of the families Erebidae and Noctuidae from Kunashir Island: **A** – *Melipotia electaria*; **B** – *Blasticorhinus unduligera*; **C** – *Hypocala subsatura*; **D** – *Amyna punctum*; **E** – *Zanclognatha obliqua*; **F** – *Diomea cremata*; **G** – *Bertula bistrigata*; **H, I** – *Chibidokuga hypenodes*; **J** – *Prometopus flavicollis*; **K** – *Stenoloba jankowskii*; **L** – *Ipimorpha subtusa*; **M** – *Chasminodes atrata*. Scale bar = 10 mm.

Figure 5. Species of the family Noctuidae from Kunashir Island: **A** – *Cosmia pyralina*; **B** – *Cosmia cara*; **C** – *Mormo muscivirens*; **D** – *Orthogonia sera*. Scale bar = 10 mm.

Figure 6. Genitalia of specimens from Kunashir Island: **A** – male genitalia of *Chrysozephyrus brillantinus*; **B** – male genitalia of *Dolbina exacta*; **C** – male genitalia of *Blasticorhinus unduligera*; **D** – male genitalia of *Chibidokuga hypenodes*; **E** – female genitalia of *Amyna punctum*.

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